

War Economy Armed Conflicts In Iraq After 2003 An Analytical Sociological Study

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 06 , 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 07 , 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Economy, Fuels, Sociological</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5610292</p>	<p><i>Modern theories in understanding conflicts focus largely on the political economy of war as a catalyst that fuels conflicts and their continuity, as Iraq is witnessing a continuous state of conflicts after 2003, and it is largely linked to the economic abundance of resources, where the various economic resources represented an economic flood that helped armed groups to form and continue, but it It has begun to establish conflicts under the pretext of religious and regional identities in order to enhance its resources through war, and this is what our current study has dismantled, and one of the most important findings of the research are /</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Because of the debts of the former regime during the Kuwait war and the Iran war, the first signs of the emergence of the war economy and the black economy were established in Iraq.</i> 2. <i>The internal conflicts operated through organized crime networks that are formed on two levels, the first during the time of the previous regime and the second after 2003.</i> 3. <i>Reliance of armed groups on illegal ways to support their economy, such as oil smuggling, money laundering, crime, and drug smuggling.</i> 4. <i>Armed groups are linked to regional and international war economy networks that support the continuation of the conflict in Iraq.</i> 5. <i>Armed groups reproduce themselves as social and political actors through national reconciliations, ending conflicts and political settlements.</i>

Introduction

The first axis

Research elements and concepts

First .search items

1. Research problem

The economy is an essential link for building and developing societies, as countries today know their economy and its ability to push its wheel forward, and Iraq as a country has an economy based on the rentier sector, which led to an imbalance in the conduct of economic operations, especially after the 2003 war, as the war greatly affected the reality of the economy Iraq in the chaos left by the war and the lack of security and safety, as was the proliferation of armed groups a significant role in the birth of the war economy , which has imposed itself clearly on the country 's economy by virtue of the nature of the activities that took place in which lies the problem of search in an attempt to answer the following questions .?Knowing the extent of the influence of armed groups on the reality of the Iraqi economy today, and whether Iraq will be able to build a free economy away from the armed conflicts that occur inside the country

2. Research importance

The importance of research.

The theoretical importance of research lies in identifying the belief of Iraq after 2003 in light of the many changes that occurred in that period, which prompted the researcher to collect information about the matter in order to analyze that period and reach results that contribute to supplying scientific libraries with sources of new information.

The practical importance of the researcher is embodied in the direct reliance on the analysis of the information obtained to draw a scientific map for that stage, which paves the way for researchers to study the subject in different ways, except from the economic, social or political aspect .

3. Research aims

- i. Getting to know the reality of the Iraqi economy after 2003.
- ii. Shedding light on the influence of armed groups on the Iraqi economy.
- iii. Identifying the social and economic reasons that contributed to the emergence of the war economy in Iraq after 2003 .

Second: research concepts

War economy War economy:

Knows Philippe Le Belon .Le Billon, Philippe The war economy is “the system of producing, mobilizing and allocating resources to support the war effort,” and thus defines it as the measures taken by the conflicting parties to support their war necessities. It is considered that its abundance helps economic growth, as it increases the risk of armed conflicts by financing and stimulating conflicts. ^[1]

As for Karen Ballentin and Heiko Nitschke Ballentine and Heiko Nitschke Karen, They define war economy as " the continuation of economics by other means , ^{[2]n} .and they go to the ways and measures in which this economy operates, as what characterizes war economies - especially in civil wars in which the government and rebels are the parties to the conflict ” - involves the circumvention and destruction of the formal economy, the growth of informal and black markets, and the rule of plunder. , extortion, violence and deliberate against civilians by militants to gain control of lucrative assets, and the exploitation of labor, and that the economy is decentralized, and thrives where dependence on smuggling. ^{[3]n}

Second axis

The reality of the Iraqi economy after 2003

After the ninth of April 2003, and until the handover of sovereignty to an Iraqi government in June 2004 ^[4]The focus was on rebuilding the country's infrastructure ^[5]especially the production of oil, electricity and water, and the identification of investment opportunities available. ^[6]

Economic reconstruction involves a radical transformation of the economic institutions of society in order to promote growth and development as well as to solve perceived economic and social problems .In most post-conflict situations, infrastructure is destroyed and roads, power stations, water pipes, hospitals, schools and sanitation facilities must be completely rebuilt .In addition to the destruction of physical capital, human capital and social capital have been seriously damaged by the conflict .Thus, the process of economic reconstruction includes rebuilding infrastructure, restoring physical, social and human capital, and restructuring fiscal, monetary and trade policies in order to allow the emergence of a strong private sector . ^[7] However, the situation took different paths from what the United States used to present in the Iraqi dream, which it portrayed in the image of the American dream in the periods between the two world wars and their aftermath.

1. Reconstruction:

Security Council Resolution 1483, Iraq's development priorities included the following:

- a -Strengthening sovereign and transparent government institutions.
- NS -Restoring basic human infrastructure and services after their decline due to poor governance and crises.
- NS -Supporting economic and social transformation that gives growth and social protection^[8].

The cost of the project, according to reports, was (36) billion dollars at the average level, in addition to an additional (20) billion dollars, according to the estimate of the destruction authority. in it . ^[9]The indicator that flows within the framework of the analysis of this study to most of the companies investing in Iraq are American companies and trained in their strategies to work in conditions of war^{1.*} , [[]and the reconstruction process was started in vague ways and for which the legal frameworks and clear means were not defined, which allowed the opportunity to exploit it for the benefit of organized terrorist and criminal networks alike.

The Amnesty International report, in its analysis of the method of investment free of legal controls under US sponsorship, pointed to concerns expressed in the following: “Some foreign companies may feel tempted to take advantage of the volatile status quo, before the formation of an Iraqi government that represents its people and is able to establish and maintain the rule of law. The other itself is trying to resolve many difficult situations in the absence of a clear national legal framework. And if there is internal discontent with the American and British presence in Iraq, companies linked to these two occupying powers will find themselves the target of attack. , companies will take steps to ensure the safety of their employees and the security of their facilities, goods and other property. In similar situations in other countries, security forces guarding companies have sometimes resorted to disproportionate use of weapons, for example against peaceful demonstrators. ^{[10]n}.

2. Privatization:

Within the economic / social transformations in Iraq is the change of the economic system, so international standards have theoretically become the basis for drawing the country's economic policies towards openness or transition towards a market economy, which is within the restructuring and economic adjustment imposed by the Bank and the International Monetary Fund .Prices are no longer determined by a government decision, but

are left to the movement of the local market to be determined by wholesale and retail traders based on the prices of importers, and these determine their prices according to the movement of the global market.

For the purpose of implementing the restructuring, the American civil governor brought together the executive and legislative authority by virtue of international resolutions. He issued 126 decisions and orders from the ninth of April to the sixth of May 2003, including 30 decisions concerned with the economic issue, and most of these decisions cast a shadow on the economic situation in Iraq in the long run. The medium and long term, which generated these decisions a dangerous phenomenon for the Iraqi economy, which is the phenomenon of

(commodity dumping), ⁽¹¹⁾ as announced by L. Paul Bremer. L. Paul Bremer On the twenty-sixth of May 2003, "Iraq is open for business", ⁽¹²⁾ "which led to the disappearance of local private and public industries, and the tariff rate on unimportant goods was supposed to increase, in the first phase of the reconstruction, in order to reduce the leakage of foreign currency out of Iraq, but the occupation authority and for political and security reasons, This was adopted to provide acceptability to the people". ⁽¹³⁾ Bremer's procedures created disparities between groups of society, groups were marginalized, equality was absent, religious, sectarian and ethnic tendencies were raised, and the concept of the homeland was absent, and it was replaced by components, which indicated a failure in all areas ⁽¹⁴⁾.

The third axis

War Economy and Continuing Conflicts

First: the contexts of the relationship between the economy and internal conflicts.

The manifestations of tendencies in the first decade after the fall of the Baathist regime continued in multiple and overlapping forms that work parallel to each other. Armed groups allied with criminal gangs proliferated strongly. According to Schultz and Dew, "The origins of these criminal gangs and networks go back to the Baath Party periods, and were greatly helped by Saddam Hussein's release of 200,000 prisoners. One of Saddam's legacy is the widespread availability of weapons, which helped spread crime." Violence is systematic and widespread ⁽¹⁵⁾. These stages can be summarized as follows :

1. The first stage: - the invasion and occupation of Iraq (random-organized violence), which is the violence that Iraq witnessed during the fall of the Baathist regime, looting, assassinations, and political and social revenge killings. Indiscriminate violence means violence emanating from separate groups in an unorganized manner, but it performs an important function for the group indirectly. In breaking the previous pattern, where it took social contexts entitled murder and assassination, as for organized violence, it is systematic violence, and the occupation forces and their opponents from Al-Qaeda at the time used it against the various social groups in Iraq. In this context, Tony Ward pointed out in his study (Transformations of Violence in Iraq) that "honor crimes in Kurdistan alone in the period 1991-2004 were more (1250 to 5000) According to the Basra Security Committee, 79 women were killed by gangs in Basra in 2007 (for violating the teachings of Islam) ⁽¹⁶⁾ "This level represented in controlling the attitudes of the population according to the geographical region in Iraq, and these crimes rose to the level of terrorism and a close relationship was formed between their practice and sowing terror and dread in the hearts of the local population. Which was practiced in Basra, whoever was killed on charges of honor or moral and intellectual perversion, was by people we know well, so and so were imprisoned in Abu Ghraib prison at the time of the grave, and after the fall - they were settled - and they became billionaire traders and even to maintain their position they took advantage of religion as a cover, and currently they are traders who do not They confess neither a religion nor anything else, the most ridiculous 24 hours you find them in nightclubs .(There were many forms of violent practices that occurred during those periods (2005 and 2006), including (double killing, shaving the hair of anyone who does not adhere to Islamic principles, breaking the leg of those who wear Bermuda... and others, and civilians were only able to accept the instructions issued by these groups Although the religious authorities, the sheikhs and the masters do not accept their actions, they monopolize and owned money and power and we are no longer able to confront. In this stage the determinants of the new war were realized - the discourse of identity, terrorizing the population, breaking the state's monopoly on the practice of violence - during this period the government was working hard, It is the young - to restore the institutional system of the state as well as social restructuring, but it loses this ability because of the active hand in managing Iraqi affairs and the state is the policy of the American occupation. The relationship was also established and developed between terrorist groups, the emergence of organized crime gangs, and they took more dangerous social and economic contexts ⁽¹⁷⁾.
2. The second stage: - the integration of organized criminal gangs into the frameworks of conflicts and identity: The civil conflicts in Iraq took two important stages, the first in 2006-2008. It is committed by organized criminal groups side by side or even incorporated into the titles of the resistance and it does

not actually belong to the resistance but is a criminal economic activity and one of them (in Saddam's era, he was involved in marginal crimes - theft, forgery and selling contraband - in 1997, after His meeting with someone persuaded him with money to join the Saddam Fedayeen, a militia affiliated with the Baath Party, in 2001 he was working directly with a group of officers in the Republican Guard supervising the smuggling of oil and drugs that run from the south (Basra) towards (Samawah) all the way to Anbar, and then Saudi Arabia and Jordan, he was present in Fallujah and Ramadi in 2004 within his previous work networks. He was targeting the American army and transportation lines that pass from the highway, whether commercial or civil, for the purpose of bargaining, after 2006 he returned to his home in Radwanayah, a suburb of Baghdad, to work in the arms and explosives trade and sell them to both parties to the conflict during the civil conflicts in Iraq in 2006, and his network expanded to include members from Baghdad, Basra, Samawah, Diyala and Mosul. And to restore the Iraqi government to impose control and security, he was forced to travel to Jordan, where he now resides .

Has seen the highest stages of the armed clash between members of the community after the bombing of the shrines of the military shrine on February 22 , 2006 , and adopted the act of al Qaeda gangs in Mesopotamia, after the death of Zarqawi ^[18] Ascended to the leadership of terrorist organizations, the youth groups who are most willing and motivated to practice violence and killing, and are more trained and prepared to use technology and communication to influence the local population, which are the new means of war. These groups have strong military experience, as the Crisis Group report indicates that "in 2004 a bulletin called (Jaish Muhammad) called on all former members of the Baath Party and the regime's intelligence services to atone for past crimes by adopting a correct behavior: "Call each other because you know each other." Some well .Organize your ranks and be an example and a support for the Mujahideen so that the people will forgive you for what you have done against them. ^{[19]c}.

Fourth Axis

War Economy and Terrorism Financing in Iraq (From Al-Qaeda to ISIS Gangs):

-1The economics of al-Qaeda's war:

After the American invasion of Iraq, and the entry of its military forces into Baghdad on April 9, 2003, al-Qaeda members infiltrated and traced their origin to a jihadist group founded in Jordan in the early 1990s, led by Ahmed Fadhil Nazzal al-Khalayleh, and his nickname Abu Musab al-Zarqawi, who formed the organization Jama'at al-Tawhid wal-Jihad in September 2003 . ^[20] In October 2004, al-Zarqawi pledged allegiance to al-Qaeda leader Osama bin Laden, and the organization's name became "Al-Qaeda of Jihad in Mesopotamia ."Thus, the deception of the Arabs continued with this jihadist organization, which pretends to fight the soldiers of the American occupation .And as soon as he gained more Iraqi elements and places, in the provinces of Nineveh, Anbar, Diyala, Kirkuk and Salah al-Din, he began killing everyone who did not support his organization, so he entered into many armed confrontations and conflicts against the armed factions of all their national, national and Islamic sects^[21].

Al-Qaeda and its mutated labels exploited the religious identity as a means to control the discourses of the population in which it was present, and began to practice its terrorist and economic activities. It preferred that al-Qaeda and then ISIS gangs be a unique subject due to the privacy and clarity of its criminal activities centered on war economies, and the activity of al-Qaeda and its generations will be discussed according to what Available from reports and documents about their economic activities.

Al-Qaeda and ISIS gangs at their beginnings during the period (2005-2010) collected funds through what can be classified mainly as criminal activities, including fundraising activities: oil smuggling, selling stolen goods, extortion, taxation, and the sale of stolen artifacts, And kidnapping for ransom, and sometimes deduction of part of the money that the Iraqi government sent to its employees, which ISIS gangs controlled later^[22].

According to the documents, the Foundation (Centre for Combating Terrorism) CTCIn 2007, it obtained lists of salaries (9271) members of the Al-Qaeda organization at the beginning of its establishment distributed over Nineveh ,(3615) Anbar (2917) and Diyala (2193) and in smaller numbers from Salah al-Din: ^[23](546)

There were several main sources of income for the organization during the second half of the first decade of the fall of the Baathist regime:

a -Oil smuggling: Obtaining oil for smuggling took a variety of routes .Either by pulling directly from the pipelines or hijacking tanker trucks, he even set up fuel gas stations to win the rights to refuel shipments .He also tried to take control of the Baiji oil refinery, which was a hotly contested asset .In 2006, it was estimated that about a third of the oil processed in the Baiji refinery went for smuggling, and in mid-2007, about 70% of the refinery's production was diverted to the black market .At the beginning of 2007, a report was issued saying that the Islamic State in Iraq had earned more than a billion dollars from smuggling oil from the Baiji refinery. ^[24]

NS -blackmail: The extortion practices followed by the organization included taking 20 % of the value of contracts from large companies in Nineveh, for example, a non-alcoholic beverage factory, cement manufacturers, and others. The Islamic State in Iraq also demanded that mobile phone companies pay sums of money in exchange for not destroying cell phone towers. At one point, that practice alone brought in \$200,000 a month from one mobile phone company. ^[25]

NS -Other criminal activities: Other illegal activities carried out by the organization included smuggling cigarettes, looting each truck in exchange for \$500 road traffic, kidnapping for ransom, and theft of construction equipment, generators, and electrical cables ^[26]. In one of the largest thefts carried out by the Islamic State in Iraq, 26 real estate ledgers including property titles worth \$90 million were stolen, which the organization later resold ^[27].

The most prominent activities of Al-Qaeda in Anbar were based on theft, smuggling and extortion, unlike the activity of the State Organization in Nineveh, which relies on oil smuggling ^[28]. And spoils, as the transportation of resources, such as oil, refined petroleum products, phosphate compounds, or even antiquities, requires intermediaries and means of transportation. In order to expand the scope of the fight against these revenues, the coalition will have to identify the middlemen and final buyers. According to the available information, al-Qaeda from June 2005 to May 2006 in Anbar raised approximately \$4.5 million, or about \$373,000 per month. The group earned about \$2.3 million—more than 51% of its income—from selling what appeared to be stolen goods, most of which were valuable capital items such as construction equipment, generators, and electrical cables. ^[29]

He notes the high activity of al-Qaeda in the areas of theft, robbery and car smuggling, which is important to him because it is one of the important weapons on which his activity is based, and that Iraq at that period was open to an economy offset by the lack of cars, and it would be a profitable business with a dual financial and criminal use (for booby traps). Also, the stolen goods include livestock and all goods seized by the organization, whether they are from (apostates) or (infidels) as described by the organization, and the highest funding rates were 2006, the year of postponing the civil war in Iraq, and this explains the logical relationship of the assumption that economic resources push conflicts to Continuation.

The dominance of the al-Qaeda gangs and the gangs (the Islamic State in Iraq) did not last long in public. The emergence of the national awakening pulled the mattress from under the possibility of dominating the youth of the provinces that it dominated, as its movement on the factors of poverty, unemployment and religious identity was no longer effective in that period. The Awakening included many young people, as mentioned in the previous pages, and then the religious identity lost its effect in the post-conflict periods of 2006, and Al-Qaeda and other terrorist organizations clashed with tribal and local forces, which transformed the areas of domination from the city centers to their margins, and this presence continued until His exploitation of the grumbling of young people and because of the poor service conditions, high unemployment and the lack of job opportunities in some western governorates of Iraq, where the ambitions of the war merchants were more than a war of identities. Money and money and the subject of the study here only dealt with the issue of the war economy for these conflicting organizations. It is worth mentioning that ISIS is one of the most dangerous and economically rich global organizations.

-2ISIS Gangs) ISIS Financing(

According to reports published by the Foreign Policy and Western economic newspapers interested in the war economy; The financial peak of ISIS (June 2015-March 2015) ISIS seized about 5.5-7 billion US dollars from oil exports, bank deposits, arms sales, antiquities smuggling, confiscation of government equipment and property, taking royalties, selling drugs, imposing taxes and zakat, observers confirm that ISIS succeeded in taking out nearly 700 million dollars through the money laundering operations of the network of the narrator "Fawaz Muhammad Jubeir Al-Rawi" outside Iraq, Syria and Libya and invested them in trade, industries, real estate and technology .. and various other investments in order to benefit from its profits after 2017, and also succeeded in investing about 400- 600 million dollars inside Iraq and Syria to be used as self-financing in each state separately, and accordingly, ISIS still holds about 1.5-2 billion dollars, and this confirms the saying that it is (the richest terrorist organization in modern history). ^[30] The wealth of ISIS comes mainly from three sources.

a -Oil and gas: In the territories it controls, the sale of these resources generated about \$500 million during 2015 through mainly internal sales, starting in the middle of the year (2015). 3 million dollars ^[31] The smuggling operations are carried out in the same ways that we mentioned above in the 2006 periods, but they differ in terms of complete control over some wells, and they also use large fleets of trucks to transport oil to the black market, and according to the reports of the International Coalition, the number of tankers exceeded 2500 ^[32] Most of the tankers who drive it are civilians, some of them work in this profession for the purpose of either survival or for the purpose of providing the money necessary for the requirements of life .

NS -Taxation and Extortion: The daily revenue of ISIS gangs has been estimated at \$1.3 million per day from multiple sources of revenue such as kidnappings for ransom, antiquities smuggling, and armed bank

robbery .As a land-holding entity, the group collects various taxes and fees from the population under its control, amounting to \$360 million in 2015^[33]

-ISIS looted and sold antiquities to fund its leadership salaries and regional ambitions .The strategy included stimulating illegal excavations in the areas it had occupied .Unemployed local residents living under ISIS occupation were encouraged to loot and sell antiquities outside ISIS areas to feed their families, and ISIS paid a 20% “khums” tax.

In 2014, ISIS began investing in excavations by carefully selecting archaeologists and experts, and when the battle against ISIS gained momentum with attacks on more prominent revenue sources, such as oil, livestock and crops, ISIS began more and more antiquities smuggling, as they tightened the rules for unauthorized looting and took control On the supply chain – from drilling to asset valuation and searching for the best online platforms to attract wealthy buyers.^[34]

NS -Banks: When ISIS seized Mosul in 2014, it succeeded in looting more than \$500 million in cash from the treasuries of the Central Bank. 41), Al-Rasheed Bank (17), Cooperative Agricultural Bank (22), Real Estate Bank (3), Trade Bank of Iraq (1(

As for the private banks, their number reached (37), namely, the Middle East Bank (3), the Economy Bank (5), the Gulf Bank (2), the Tigris and Euphrates Bank (1), the National Bank of Iraq (1), the Mosul Bank (12), the Bank of Baghdad (5) and the North Bank (2) Ashur Bank (2) and Al-Iraqi Islamic Bank ,^[35] (4) as well as the (1900) exchange offices, banks.^[36]

NS -Remittances and electronic currencies: After the defeat of ISIS gangs in Iraq, and despite its large financial balance, according to some of the reports we mentioned above, it is still working to stimulate funding through multiple means from it.

NS -Charitable Networks and Organizations as Frontiers for Funding:

These funds obtained by ISIS and accepted by al-Qaeda networks, organized criminal gangs and the shadow military were invested in most of them through money laundering and have turned into economic empires that the Iraqi government is working hard to combat, through its legislation of Law (39) of 2015 as well as its joining the Financial Action Group to Combat Money Laundering and financing terrorism, and it has succeeded in getting it out of the black area into the gray area.

From a sociological point of view, money laundering can be read from the infiltration of illegal funds into society that upsets the balance of social construction in the country and the rise of criminals responsible for the money laundering process to the hierarchy of society, while the decline of middle-class employees, unemployed educated and others to the bottom of the base.

The money laundering process also leads to the spread of crimes in societies in all its forms, as the social criterion for the value of the individual becomes money regardless of its source and aspects of its activity .Not to mention that the war drained both material and human capital, and this cost is enough to restructure the social system and its class divisions.

The most important search results are: I

1. Because of the debts of the former regime during the Kuwait war and the Iran war, the first signs of the emergence of the war economy and the black economy were established in Iraq.
2. The internal conflicts operated through organized crime networks that are formed on two levels, the first during the time of the previous regime and the second after 2003.
3. Reliance of armed groups on illegal ways to support their economy, such as oil smuggling, money laundering, crime, and drug smuggling.
4. Armed groups are linked to regional and international war economy networks that support the continuation of the conflict in Iraq.
5. The control of armed groups such as ISIS gangs on most areas of Iraq because of their economic capacity in return for the weak economic support by the state to the residents of the areas under its control.
6. The integration of armed groups within the framework of the national identity and their attempt to find their own identity that reflects the actions they take within society to give it the status of legitimacy.
7. Armed groups reproduce themselves as social and political actors through national reconciliations, ending conflicts and political settlements

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